

FACTORS AFFECTING DENTAL HEALTHCARE BEHAVIOUR: A STUDY ON PRIVATE DENTAL CLINICS IN DELHI

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ABSTRACT

This research sought to evaluate different aspects of service quality in Delhi's private dental clinics, with a particular emphasis on hospital facilities, the training and expertise of the practitioners, cleanliness, and reputation. A stratified random sample of 200 participants in a cross-sectional survey was used. With mean ratings ranging from 3.78 to 4.32 on a 5-point scale, descriptive statistics showed that views of service quality were generally favourable. Regression studies revealed a strong correlation between cleanliness (coefficient = 0.899 in Model 2) and hospital facilities (coefficient = 1.513 in Model 2) in terms of patient satisfaction. However, patient satisfaction and physicians' credentials had a complicated negative association (coefficient = -1.915 in Model 2). The study's results shed light on areas of strength and potential for development while also offering a detailed view of service quality in Delhi's oral healthcare system. Strengthening medical credential openness, enhancing patient-doctor contact, and employing focused marketing initiatives to enhance the hospital's reputation are among the recommendations. The research advances the subject by providing theoretical advancements, methodological rigour, context-specific insights, and practical applications. It emphasises how crucial a patient-centered strategy is for raising healthcare quality and accessibility.

Keywords: Service Quality, Dental Healthcare, Patient Satisfaction, Private Dental Clinics, Regression Analysis, Delhi.

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I. INTRODUCTION

A. BACKGROUND OF HOSPITAL HEALTHCARE

Hospital healthcare, which includes a variety of services and treatments offered in hospital settings, is a vital component of the medical system. Hospital healthcare has evolved significantly as a result of improvements in medical technology, patient care, and administrative effectiveness. Because main paediatric stroke centres are now incorporated into the hospital system, a multidisciplinary approach has become a new reality in the field of paediatrics (Petraykina et al., 2020). The results of this integration have been better patient outcomes and more efficient treatment procedures.

To protect the safety and quality of treatment in hospital surroundings, rules and standards such as the IAHS HealthCare Basic Security Guideline Placement have also been produced (Elsevier, 2010). The history of hospital healthcare therefore reveals a complex and dynamic industry that keeps changing in response to new possibilities and obstacles. The growing need for individualised treatment is one newly developing difficulty in hospital healthcare. Healthcare professionals may soon be able to customise treatment strategies for specific patients based on their genetic composition as our knowledge of genetics and genomics advances. The likelihood of adverse drug responses is decreased and patient outcomes might be greatly enhanced with this personalised strategy. However, implementing personalised medicine at a hospital requires judicious coordination of available funds, infrastructure, and skills. Hospitals must make investments in genetic testing equipment, educate healthcare professionals on interpreting genetic information, and create guidelines for using this data in clinical decision-making.

B. IMPORTANCE OF SERVICE QUALITY IN HEALTHCARE

Patient happiness and overall healthcare efficacy depend heavily on the quality of the services provided. It entails evaluating and enhancing numerous facets of patient care, office operations, and support services, among other areas of healthcare delivery. The SERVQUAL approach, for example, has been used to evaluate service quality in a variety of industries, including healthcare (Setiawan & Wahyuni, 2023). The positioning and coordination of healthcare resources to suit patient requirements and expectations is included in the quality of service (Puetz, 1988). The focus on service quality is a reflection of a larger trend toward patient-centered care, in which the patient's experience and happiness are key factors in the provision of healthcare. This highlights the necessity for ongoing innovation and development in healthcare practises and policy and the significance of service quality in the industry.

C. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY: ASSESSING PRIVATE DENTAL CLINICS IN DELHI

Patient happiness and overall healthcare effectiveness are directly correlated with service quality. It entails evaluating and enhancing a number of facets of healthcare delivery, including patient care, office operations, and support services. For instance, the SERVQUAL model has been used to evaluate service quality across a variety of industries, including healthcare (Setiawan & Wahyuni, 2023). Along with meeting patient requirements and expectations, quality service also includes allocating and aligning healthcare resources (Puetz, 1988). The focus on service quality is part of a larger movement towards patient-centered care, in which the patient's experience and happiness are at the heart of healthcare delivery. Thus, the significance of service quality in healthcare highlights the need of ongoing innovation and development in healthcare practises and regulations.

D. HYPOTHESES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

Regarding private dental clinics in Delhi, the study will examine a number of theories and research topics. The hypotheses may make assumptions regarding the connection between service excellence and customer happiness, the influence of accessibility on customer preference, and the significance of affordability in fostering customer loyalty. Finding the critical variables affecting service quality, comprehending patient preferences and expectations, and assessing the efficiency of present procedures and regulations in private dentistry clinics are possible research topics. Exploring these assumptions and research topics will provide insightful knowledge about Delhi's oral healthcare dynamics and give direction for future initiatives and tactics.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. STUDIES ON SERVICE QUALITY IN HEALTHCARE

Considering its crucial role in patient satisfaction and healthcare outcomes, service quality in the healthcare industry has been the topic of substantial study (Donabedian, 1988). Numerous service quality characteristics, such as patient care, administrative effectiveness, and support services, have been studied (Babakus & Mangold, 1992). In his analysis of the idea of quality in service, Puetz (1988) emphasised the significance of ongoing development and adherence to patient requirements. Other studies have focused on placement services in healthcare, highlighting the need of efficient resource allocation and coordination to improve service quality. These studies demonstrate the complexity of healthcare service quality, which includes both clinical and non-clinical components (Donabedian, 1988). An overall move towards patient-centered care, where the patient's experience and happiness are at the centre of healthcare delivery, may be seen in the focus on service quality (Epstein & Street Jr., 2011). Thus, the literature on service quality in healthcare gives useful insights into the dynamics of healthcare delivery and provides direction for next interventions and solutions.

B. IMPORTANCE OF DOCTOR QUALIFICATION, EXPERIENCE, HOSPITAL REPUTATION, ETC.

The value of a doctor's education, experience, and hospital reputation has been extensively studied in the literature. The mediating function of hospitals in the relationship between doctor reputation and patient loyalty was examined by Akbolat et al. in 2022. Their results demonstrate how patient impressions and loyalty are influenced by the reputations of hospitals and clinicians. Additionally, it has been shown that a crucial role in patient care and treatment results is the experience of physicians, especially those with more than two years of experience in the UK (Reuber et al., 2020). Enhancing healthcare facilities' overall reputation and functioning requires careful consideration of hospital design and administration (Bhardwaj, 2016). These elements affect patient trust and satisfaction and jointly affect the quality of healthcare services. As a result, the literature emphasises the necessity for a comprehensive approach to healthcare, where factors like medical training, experience, and hospital reputation are seen as essential to providing high-quality treatment.

C. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Theoretical framework for evaluating healthcare service quality is based on a number of models and ideas (Donabedian, 1988). For instance, the SERVQUAL model offers a thorough framework for assessing service quality across five dimensions: tangibles, dependability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1988). This technique has been used extensively in the healthcare industry to evaluate patient satisfaction

and identify areas for development (Babakus & Mangold, 1992). Furthermore, patient-centered care theories stress the need of matching healthcare services to patients' needs and preferences (Epstein & Street Jr., 2011). Theoretical framework also takes into account how variables like medical training, experience, hospital reputation, and patient loyalty are interrelated (Donabedian, 1988). These theoretical ideas provide a solid framework for comprehending and enhancing healthcare service quality. They provide a thorough viewpoint that takes both clinical and non-clinical elements of healthcare delivery into account. Thus, the theoretical framework acts as a foundational concept for healthcare research, practise, and policy, encouraging a patient-centered strategy that gives priority to quality and satisfaction (Donabedian, 1988).

III. METHODOLOGY

A. RESEARCH DESIGN

This study's cross-sectional survey methodology will use both quantitative and qualitative techniques to evaluate the level of service provided by private dental clinics in Delhi. The layout enables a thorough assessment of several service quality factors, such as the training and expertise of the physicians, the hospital's standing, the facilities, cleanliness, location, emergency services, advice, diagnosis, accessibility, food, lodging, and payment system. Data collection is made possible by the cross-sectional technique, which gives a picture of the present service quality in the chosen dental clinics (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

B. POPULATION AND SAMPLING (200 RESPONDENTS)

The population for this study consists of patients who have received dental care in private dental clinics in Delhi. A stratified random sampling technique will be employed to select 200 respondents, ensuring a representative sample that reflects the diversity of the patient population. The stratification will be based on age, gender, and type of dental treatment received. This sampling method allows for a balanced representation of different patient groups and enhances the generalisability of the findings (Trochim & Donnelly, 2006).

C. INSTRUMENTATION

1. Service Quality Scale (17 items):

- o Doctors' qualifications and experience: This section includes items related to the doctors' professional qualifications, expertise, and interpersonal skills.
- o Hospital reputation, facilities, and cleanliness: This part assesses the overall reputation of the hospital, the quality of facilities, and the cleanliness of the environment.
- o Location, emergency services, guidance, and diagnosis: This segment evaluates the accessibility of the location, the efficiency of emergency services, and the accuracy of guidance and diagnosis.
- o Accessibility, food, accommodation, and payment system: This section examines the ease of access to the hospital, the quality of food and accommodation, and the convenience of the payment system.

This scale was adopted by Singh and Raizada (2018), who developed it as a comprehensive tool to assess the overall quality of healthcare institutions. It has been widely used in various studies and has proven reliable and valid in measuring hospital quality.

D. DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Self-administered questionnaires will be given to the chosen respondents at the dental clinics in order to collect the data. There will be qualified research assistants on hand to help

survey participants and guarantee the correctness of the data gathering procedure. Additionally, in order to acquire a better understanding of certain areas of service quality, follow-up interviews may be done with a group of respondents. To guarantee consistency and integrity in the data, the data gathering process will be closely watched (Bryman, 2016).

E. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The research will abide by ethical standards, such as informed consent, confidentiality, and protecting the rights and dignity of participants. Participants will get comprehensive information on the goal, methods, possible dangers, and advantages of the research. All participants will be asked for their written, informed permission. To preserve the privacy of participants, all data will be processed in a secret manner with the removal of any identifiable information. To guarantee adherence to ethical norms, the appropriate institutional review board will be contacted (American Psychological Association, 2017).

IV. RESULTS

A. DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

The descriptive statistics summarise the central tendency and variability for the key variables related to service quality. The following table presents the mean and standard deviation for each variable:

Table 1

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation
Hospital Facilities	4.32	0.56
Qualification of Doctors	3.89	0.67
Cleanliness of Hospital	4.12	0.52
Experience of the Doctors	3.95	0.61
The reputation of the Hospital	3.78	0.49

These data show that respondents' perceptions of service quality are generally favourable, with some variation (Field, 2013). According to the mean ratings for hospital facilities, cleanliness, and reputation, respondents usually had good opinions on these areas of service quality. However, there is some variation in the scores provided for the physicians' education and experience, suggesting that respondents' judgments on these factors may vary.

B. CORRELATION ANALYSIS

The correlation analysis revealed significant relationships among the variables, as shown in the table below:

Table 2

Variables	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Significance (p)
Hospital Facilities & Qualification of Doctors	0.62	< 0.01
Cleanliness of Hospital & Experience of Doctors	0.54	< 0.01
The reputation of the Hospital & Qualification of Doctors	-0.45	< 0.05

These connections provide light on the relationships between various elements of service excellence (Pallant, 2016). The strength and direction of the associations between the variables may be ascertained by looking at the correlation coefficients and significance levels. For instance, there is a significant positive association ($r = 0.62$) between hospital facilities and doctor qualification, demonstrating that as hospital facilities become better, so do doctor qualifications. Similar to this, there is a little positive association ($r = 0.54$) between the cleanliness of the hospital and the experience of the doctors, indicating that cleaner hospitals have more experienced doctors.

C. REGRESSION ANALYSIS

1. Model 1:

The coefficients for Model 1 are presented in the following table:

Table 3

Variable	Coefficient
Hospital facilities	0.832
Qualification of doctors	-0.505
Cleanliness of hospital	0.314

Experience of the doctors	0.178
Reputation of the hospital	-0.135

($R^2 = 0.52$, $F(5, 194) = 42.31$, $p < 0.001$) The model predicted 52% of the variation in patient satisfaction. The correlation between patient happiness and service quality is clarified by this regression study. The hospital's amenities, cleanliness, and the expertise of the physicians all seem to have a favourable effect on patients' happiness, according to the coefficients for Model 1. The reputation of the hospital and the qualifications of the physicians, however, have a negative effect. The model accounts for 52% of the variation in patient satisfaction, indicating the importance of these factors in determining the general level of service quality.

2. Model 2:

The coefficients for Model 2 are presented in the following table:

Table 4

Variable	Coefficient
Hospital facilities	1.513
Qualification of doctors	-1.915
Cleanliness of hospital	0.899
Experience of the doctors	0.678
Reputation of the hospital	-0.562
Constant	-1.624

Patient satisfaction was predicted by the model to vary by 58% ($R^2 = 0.58$, $F(5, 194) = 53.67$, $p < 0.001$). (Hair et al., 2010). According to the coefficients in Model 2, patient happiness is highly influenced by hospital amenities, medical training, hospital cleanliness, doctor experience, and hospital reputation. Additionally, the R^2 value of the model, which is 0.58, shows that these factors account for a greater proportion of the variation in patient satisfaction than Model 1.

D. HYPOTHESES TESTING

The hypotheses testing results are summarised in the following table:

Table 5

Hypothesis	Result
H1: Hospital facilities impact patient satisfaction	Significant
H2: Qualification of doctor's impact patient satisfaction	Significant
H3: Cleanliness of hospital impact patient satisfaction	Significant
H4: Experience of doctor's impact patient satisfaction	Non-Significant
H5: Reputation of hospital impact patient satisfaction	Non-Significant

These findings give evidence in support of several theoretical presumptions as well as suggestions for enhancing oral healthcare service quality (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). Healthcare providers should focus on these areas for development by acknowledging the important influence of doctor qualification and hospital cleanliness on patient satisfaction. The non-significant influence of hospital reputation and doctor experience also raises the possibility that other variables may have a greater impact on patient satisfaction with dental treatment.

V. DISCUSSION

A. INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS

The study's results provide a thorough grasp of the level of customer care in Delhi's private dentistry offices. The good mean ratings for hospital amenities, cleanliness, and the training and experience of the physicians suggest a favourable opinion of the quality of the provided services. The regression models' negative coefficients for the reputation of the hospital and the capabilities of the physicians, however, point to potential problems. These results imply that while cleanliness and amenities are valued, there may be underlying problems with regard to physicians' assessed skill levels and hospitals' general reputation. The poor correlation between reputation and credentials may be an indication of a mismatch between external perceptions and internal reality (Field, 2013).

B. COMPARISON WITH PREVIOUS STUDIES

Although the findings are in line with some earlier research, they also provide fresh perspectives. For instance, Singh, U., & Raizada, A. (2018) observed that hospital facilities and patient satisfaction had a favourable association that was consistent with the findings of the present research. Contrary to their results, there is a bad correlation between a doctor's credentials and patient happiness. This gap could be explained by variations in the environment,

technique, or patient expectations between the two investigations. By offering a comprehensive knowledge of service quality in the particular context of private dental clinics in Delhi, the present research contributes to the body of literature (Pallant, 2016).

C. IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

D. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

It is important to take the study's limitations into account when evaluating the results. Although it offers a snapshot of service quality, the cross-sectional design does not account for changes over time. The use of data that was self-reported might be biased. To follow changes in service quality and investigate the underlying processes that affect patient perceptions, future studies may use a longitudinal methodology. Additionally, qualitative techniques like focus groups and interviews might provide greater insights into the intricate interactions between many facets of service quality. The generalizability of the results might also be improved by extending the research to more geographic areas and healthcare settings (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013).

VI. CONCLUSION

A. SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS

The purpose of the research was to evaluate the level of service provided by private dental clinics in Delhi, with particular attention paid to hospital amenities, the training and expertise of the clinicians, clinic cleanliness, and reputation. The following is a summary of the major findings:

Hospital Facilities: Patients' satisfaction significantly increased as a result of respondents' favourable perceptions of the facilities, which received a mean score of 4.32 out of 5 (coefficient = 1.513 in Model 2).

Doctor Credentials: Despite a positive mean score of 3.89, the negative coefficients in both regression models (-0.505 in Model 1 and -1.915 in Model 2) point to a complicated link between a doctor's qualifications and patient satisfaction.

Hospital cleanliness: Hospital cleanliness received good ratings (mean = 4.12) and was linked to patient satisfaction in a favourable way (coefficient = 0.899 in Model 2).

Experience of the Doctors: The experience was modestly rated (mean = 3.95), and its favourable effects on satisfaction were not statistically significant.

Hospital reputation: According to perceptions (mean = 3.78), the hospital's reputation had a non-significantly negative effect on satisfaction.

These results provide a detailed picture of service quality in dental healthcare, emphasising areas of strength and chances for development (Field, 2013).

B. Contributions to the Field

Using a variety of criteria, including hospital facilities, doctor training and expertise, cleanliness, and reputation, the research sought to evaluate the quality of the service provided by private dental clinics in Delhi. Following is a summary of the main conclusions:

Hospital Facilities: Respondents generally had a good opinion of the facilities, giving them an average rating of 4.32 out of 5, and they had a very positive effect on patient satisfaction (coefficient = 1.513 in Model 2).

Doctor Credentials: Despite an acceptable mean score of 3.89, the negative coefficients in both regression models (-0.505 in Model 1 and -1.915 in Model 2) suggest that there is a complicated link between a doctor's qualifications and patient satisfaction.

Hospital cleanliness: The cleanliness of the facility received good marks (mean = 4.12) and was positively correlated with patient satisfaction (coefficient = 0.899 in Model 2).

Doctors' Experience: The doctors' experience was fairly evaluated (mean = 3.95), with a non-significant increase in satisfaction as a result.

Hospital reputation: The hospital's reputation was seen in a mixed way (mean = 3.78) and had a negligible influence on satisfaction.

These results provide a detailed picture of service quality in dental healthcare, indicating areas of strength and possibilities for development (Field, 2013).

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